

The Moderating Role of Language Difference in the Relationship between Virtual Consumers' Marketing Communications and Consumers' Loyalty

Niu Xiongying & Worku Habtegebriel Guluma

Abstract:

This study aims to build and test virtual consumers' marketing communications and consumers' loyalty model. In addition, the study also examined the moderating role of language differences in the relationship between virtual consumers' marketing communications and consumers' loyalty. Responses from 251 respondents were analyzed through multiple linear hierarchical regression analysis. The findings indicate that consumers' marketing communications significantly positive influence on the consumers' loyalty. However, the language differences weaken the positive relationship consumers' marketing communications and consumers' loyalty. This paper has important implications for theory and practice. In addition, the context of a non-individualistic culture, that is, Chinese context has significant implication for others collectivists cultures.

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About Author (s)

Niu Xiongying, Business School, University of International Business and Economics, Beijing, 100029, P.R. China

Worku Habtegebriel Guluma (corresponding author), Business School, University of International Business and Economics, Beijing, 100029, P.R. China

1. Introduction

The principal agenda of the study is illustrating virtual consumers' marketing communications' effects on consumers' loyalty and the moderating roles of language differences in the relations of consumers' marketing communications' effects on consumers' loyalty. As, Graca & Barry, (2017) noted effective communications play great roles in constructing consumers' communications that put forward great benefits in shaping the life span of a relationship. However, it is not well explored about the complex interaction within cross-national culture & virtual consumer's communications' effectiveness about loyalty (Butkouskaya, Llonch-Andreu, & Alarcón-del-Amo, 2020; Kim & Lee, 2010). So, the relativity of cross-national culture and virtual consumers' communications need to be explored cross-nationally among countries of diverse cultures along with economies. Then, it is surprisingly promoting the rising of the research curiosity internationally since communication effectiveness is fixed in culture. According to Wang et al. (2016) cross-national culture is the most powerful factor that can influence individual communication effectiveness to the states of loyalty towards virtual marketing communications. Therefore, cross-national culture affects satisfaction, & loyalty. Yet, the indication is dispersed & understanding of the influence is not well explored. Moreover, consumers' satisfaction, & loyalty on the way to SMLs are well impacted by culture (Rahimi & Kozak, 2017). Amazingly, cross-national culture has influences on virtual communities.

Virtual consumers' communication according to Yunhong Hao, Farooq & Yuan Sun, (2018) has been also recognized as the best valuable human act in this modern world human way of life. On the other hand, one of the cultural components & means of communication is language. It plays the role of communication & reflection. Then, cross-cultural virtual communication is crucial to perform the corporate social responsibility of virtual consumers. Cross-cultural virtual consumers' marketing communications have to be widely discussed to express the crucially, effective communications in strategic objectives (Keillor, Owens, & Pettijohn, 2001). Therefore, as Yunhong Hao, Farooq & Yuan Sun, (2018) noted in understanding the driving forces of consumers' satisfaction, & loyalty. Consequently, business firms need to develop virtual marketing communications. So, the cross-cultural virtual consumers' communication reasoning and theories ought to be given due to weights in this ubiquitous internet era. The world people numbered in billions use the internet for both individual & corporate purposes (Wan et al., 2019). Then, this reality shows that cross-cultural virtual consumers' communications are highly decisive in the modern world. Therefore, virtual marketing communications have significant influences on consumers. So, if national culture lacks due considerations negative influences can occur on consumers' & vendors' business life. Thus, cross-national culture virtual communications have to be examined continuously to introduce new perspectives about new ways of living & values. Therefore, this study probes some key elements of the influence of cross-national culture on virtual consumers' communications' effectiveness issues and provides a framework for generating a good advantage for businesses to be engaged in international commerce from the consumer's perspective.

2. Literature and hypothesis development

2.1 *The virtual Consumers' marketing communications' and consumer loyalty*

The offered study model demonstrates the influence of cross-culture on the effectiveness of virtual consumers' communication effectiveness to the states of consumers' perceived value, intimacy, trust, satisfaction, and loyalty. It is described in the way it helps to scrutinize & put forward the effect of cross-culture on consumers' cognitive & affective states of communications. At the end of the study, the effect of cross-culture on consumers'

communications effectiveness in consideration of the cognitive & affective states of consumers' to the states of consumers' perceived value, intimacy, trust, satisfaction, and loyalty will be analyzed. As long as this occurrence is considered it is a verification of the influence of cross-culture on communication effectiveness to improve consumers' cognitive & affective states to consumers' perceived value, intimacy, trust, satisfaction & loyalty. Thus, based on the above evaluation, it can be inferred that cross-cultural communications of goods & services can influence consumers' to the states of consumers' perceived value, intimacy, trust, satisfaction, and loyalty on M.C. on social network cues. Then, the study applies the social cognitive theory, Hofstede's theory of culture, communication theory & the SOR model to analyze M.C. concepts of virtual consumers' communication in consideration of cross-culture that contribute a lot to impact perceived value, intimacy, trust, satisfaction, and loyalty.

Mobile commerce constructs in case of consumers' interactions, rankings, reviews, & recommendations are stimuli that virtual sellers can utilize to pressure consumers' emotional and cognitive assessments. Consumers' virtual communications are considered as organisms that are interpreted concerning facts together with the cognitive conditions of virtual consumers' communications the emotional conditions of consumers' communications and the points of trust in manufactured goods commendations (Chen, Lu, & Wang, 2017; Li, 2019; Yadav&Rahman, 2017). The study practices communal occurrence, informational & communal support to indicate the cognitive states of consumer's virtual communications, whereas intimacy and acquaintance are used to identify the emotional conditions of virtual consumers' communications. Virtual consumers' mobile commerce intentions are practiced to define consumers' behavioral responses. As Kang & Johnson, (2013) verified mobile commerce concepts & cognitive states of virtual consumers' communications at M.C. sites offer display places on which consumers can communicate with contacts. For instance, consumers can precise their opinions on bought goods or services. The structures of social web sites can make easy friendliness by offering real constructs to social virtual communications in the world. Expert in communication can give ratings, reviews & recommendations, yet consumers can think through the content that it will be sponsored & discount it as commercially motivated. As far as the scholars' study mobile commerce web sites provide ratings reviews & referrals to the consumers in written & audiovisuals. Virtual consumers take into consideration these constructs differently. The consumers regard the ratings, reviews & referrals constructs more credibly the ones that they get from their peers than from that of paid professionals. Therefore this hypothesis is proposed:

H1: *Virtual consumers' market communications' put forth a positive effect on consumers' loyalty.*

2.2 Moderating role of language differences

Hofstede's theory of culture (Hofstede & Bond, 1984) reveals that variations in culture are the main causes for the variation of consumers' behavior to trust, satisfaction & loyalty. Gaps in the understanding can be removed by solving suspicion feeling when feeling uncertainty. So, when one removes the degree of uncertainty, he /she becomes highly convinced of the matter. Yin, Wang, Xia, and Gu (2019) noted that the more uncertainty is avoided, the more virtual consumers get trust, satisfaction, and loyalty. So, uncertainty is the main cause or factor that affects an individual's decision-making to the states of consumers' perceived value intimacy, trust, satisfaction, and loyalty in the virtual marketing communications arena. Besides, consumers' virtual marketing communications have an influential factor in consumers' decision making in mobile commerce web site platforms. The more one makes virtual marketing communications, the more one is convinced to make decisions. Thus, the

impacts of national culture, virtual consumers' communications, perceived value. Trust, satisfaction, and loyalty need further examination and analysis concerning mobile commerce websites. Moreover, national culture in the virtual consumers' communications needs due attention. Because of cross-national culture incongruence, uncertainty can occur that influences the consumers' decision-making to the goods, services, and website. Besides virtual consumers are less tolerant of ambiguous issues that they perceive from virtual marketing communications' websites. Removing barrier of communications lead to doubt escaping that puts forth optimistic effects on consumers' perceived value, intimacy, trust, satisfaction, and loyalty. . .

Cultural constructs have multi faces. The basic dimensions of cultural constructs are the value that is given ob individualism against collectivism. According to many scholarly works, the central meaning of individualism is affording the main concern to private goals more than a group or common goals. On the other hand, collectivism is the opposite of individualism. So, the central meaning of collectivism is affording main concern to common or interdependent goals more than personal or private goals. Generally, individualism prefers a self-governing relationship and goal. Whereas, collectivism gives precedence for collective or group governing relationship and goal. The dichotomy of individualism-collectivism significantly reflects the emphasis of cultural level ought to be given (Zhang and Gelb, 2010). Therefore the diversified cultures of the world people are communicated differently and there are visible differences between cultures. One can win and gain success if culturally congruent interactivities are being done. Thus this hypothesize is proposed.

H2: *Language difference moderates the correlation between consumers' virtual communications & loyalty.*

2.3 Research model

The below figure 1 shows the relationships between virtual consumers' market communications, consumers' loyalty, and language differences variables.

Figure1: Hypothesized model

Methodology

2.4 Sample and procedure

The research has undergone experimental data analysis using data collected through a survey of virtual international consumers who have experienced mobile commerce being found in China. The data brought from virtual consumers living in China are adequate, very recent, and descriptive for variables on the dependent variable. China was chosen on the foundation of mobile commerce websites retails do well at this time. The demographic categorizations in the data collections include nationality, age, gender, income, and educational background. The study samples could be collected by distributing an `online questionnaire using a purposive and systematic method of data gathering techniques from virtual consumers of diverse populations. Finally, we get 251 useful responses from the respondents.

2.5 Measures

Virtual Consumers' Marketing Communication. The scale for virtual communication effectiveness has been developed by combining the existing and newly developed measures. Virtual communication can be measured according to Hao, Farooq, and Sun (2018) by informatively, awarding consumers for giving them the confidence to make notified judgments, interactivity, explains costs of goods & services,(dealing with the consumer), creativity, rating(assessment), reviewing, accurate explanations of fees, Empathy and listening skills, reasonable goods and services analyses, two- way interactions(interactivity in a non-native language) & conceptual meaning fullness, recommendations & Creativity.

Consumers' Loyalty. According to As Yinet. al., (2019); Rambaocas, Kiripani, & Simms, (2018), the scale for consumers' loyalty has been developed by combining the existing and newly developed measures According to Nicholas et. al. (2019), with cognitive, emotional, motivational, and physical components so having strong relationships(spend more with the company), perceiving to be credible (credibly to the company), frequency of buying, loyal. Repeat purchase intentions (preferring to purchase); pay price premiums and remain or feeling loyal are the measures of loyalty.

Language differences. According to Kauret. al., (2019) & theory of culture by Hofstede cross-culture difference, influences to convenience, failure to understand the message, the barrier of language usage, decency, uncertainty, (lacking) short & long term orientations, influence on shopping habit effectiveness, employees of subsidiaries serving in different cultures, religions & language are some of the measures of cross-culture.

3. Results

The analysis of this study has been accomplished by applying SPSS version 20. The latest research tried to achieve Anderson&Gerbing, (1988) two steps investigative come up to regression analyses. Firstly, demographic variables that reveal the processes of the survey of the data gathering of the study fully in the demographic variables model conducted in Table-1, which states about demographic variables, their frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations.

To control the effects of control variables like (age, sex, & education), the partial association's process was applied to work out partial association coefficients. These explain the linear association among the variables. The correlation value of the independent variable (VCMC), dependent variables (CPV<CI & CL), and moderating variables (L.D.) have been included in table-3 along with the means, standard deviations & square root values of AVE for the variables.

Table 1: Demographic variables (N=251)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
Nationality			1.56	0.96
African	161	64.1		
Asian	62	24.7		
European	15	6.0		
USA	3	1.2		
Latin American	10	4.0		
Age			2.06	0.68
18-28 years	48	19.1		
29-38 years	141	56.2		
39-48 years	60	23.9		
49 and above	2	.8		
Gender			1.33	0.47
Male	168	66.9		
Female	83	33.1		
Education			2.35	0.65
Undergraduate	24	9.6		
Master	117	46.6		
PhD	109	43.4		
Exchange Programme	1	.4		
Monthly Income			2.01	0.47
1-2500 RMB	26	10.4		
2501-5000 RMB	195	77.7		
5001 and above	29	11.6		

The correlation analysis has revealed significant positive correlations among the independent variable (VCMC), dependent variables (CPV< CI and CL). To check the discriminate validity, Fornell&Larckers, (1981) recommendations were followed to measure the validity of the constructs. Discriminate validity should exist so long as the square root of the AVE of the construct has been higher than the correlation among the constructs (see table -2), indicates that every construct contains excellent discriminate validity, Fornell&Larckers. (1981).

Table-2: Descriptive statistics, correlations & discriminant validity

Variables	Mean	SD	α	VCMC	L.D.	CL
VCMC	3.95	0.61	0.76	(0.71)		
L.D.	2.43	1.06	0.89	-0.21**	(0.81)	
CL	3.90	0.84	0.72	0.54**	-0.22**	(0.78)

Note: *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; parentheses indicate the square root of AVE.

To test the hypothesized relationship, SPSS version 20 was applied for doing a hierarchy regression analysis besides the outcomes have been shown within table 3. Demographic variables like age, sex, as well as educational background have been controlled to decrease the effect on the outcome. To test hypothesis 1, regression analysis was performed (Table 3). The results indicates that VMC has a significant positive influence on the CL ($\beta = .721$, $p < 0.01$), which approve and support our hypothesis 1.

Table 3: Regression Analyses

Variables	Consumers' Loyalty		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Age	-.026 (.087)	-.075 (.074)	-.077 (.074)
Gender	.240*** (.115)	.051 (.102)	.047 (.102)
Education	.167** (.092)	.042 (.080)	.042 (.080)
VMC		.721*** (.076)	.717*** (.077)
L.D.		-.078* (.045)	-.076* (.046)
VMC_x_L.D.			-.118** (.053)
R ²	.026	.312	.337
ΔR ²	---	.286***	.025***
F	2.206	22.212***	18.463***

Note: *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001. Parentheses indicate standard errors (SE).

To test hypothesis 2 the same techniques were followed as the earlier one. Controlled variables had been regressed to the result variable CL After that VMC & L.D. as shown in table 3. In model 3, the consistent values of interaction terms (VMC*L.D.) had been regressed to - C, by controlling the demographics. So, the negative & significant relationship between the interaction term and CL ($\beta = -.118, p < 0.01$) shows that L.D. plays a significant role between VCMC and CL as moderator. Thus, these results proved hypothesis 2. That states language difference contains moderation function for the association within VCMC & consumers' loyalty. The simple slope test show in Figure 2 also confirms this result.

Figure 2: Moderating role language differences in the relationship between VMC and CL.

4. Discussion

The aim of this study was to text the direct relationship and effects of virtual consumers' marketing communications' (VCMC) to the affective and cognitive states of consumers' loyalty (CL). Moreover, we also aimed to check the moderating effects of language difference (L.D.) in between the relationship of consumers' trust(CT) to consumers' loyalty(CL). Generally, the directly positive relationship effects of virtual consumers' marketing communications' (VCMC) to the variables, the moderation roles of language difference(L.D.) in this study have

been supported by theories, prior literature, and the data analysis results proves. The significantly positive relationship between virtual consumer marketing communications and consumers' perceived value was established and found in prior studies. Thus, Hao, et al., (2018) noted that virtual consumers' marketing communications' interactivity, rating, and reviews contain significant optimistic results on perceived values of consumers. The worthiness of goods & services, reasonability in pricing, giving value for the money, fairness of the pricing, ought to be communicated to create good perception towards the goods and services and as well as the mobile website and its retails. Haji (2015) also viewed that consistency in the interaction of the real quality of items is some of the factors affecting perceived value. Moreover, good perceived value towards a business firm and its accommodations can be acquired and promoted through using elements of communications to brand perception. The significantly positive relationship between virtual consumers' marketing communications and consumer's intimacy was established and found in prior studies, also. As, Yin et. al., (2019) noted virtual consumers 'marketing communications have a significant relationship with consumers' intimacy among consumers and business firms. Information communications between consumers and firms' retail also have effects on consumers' opinions, characteristics, and behaviors in social networks. Besides, Kang et. al., (2015) verified that mobile commerce concepts & cognitive states of virtual consumers' communications at M.C. sites offer display places on which consumers can communicate with friends. The structures of social web sites can make easy friendliness by offering real constructs using social virtual consumers' communications' rating, reviews & recommendations. Similarly, the significantly positive relationship between virtual consumers' marketing communications and consumers' loyalty was also established and found in prior studies. Loyalty, as Rambocas, Kiripani, and Simms, (2018) noted that consumers need to get their expectations all the time to be loyal consumers. So, loyalty needs consistent cultivations. Developing loyal consumers needs strong efforts in terms of meeting consumers & their expectations. Thus consistent interactions with consumers, referrals, reviews, and ratings, information, opinions, and suggestions are very crucial to create trust and satisfaction for loyalty. Then, virtual consumers' marketing communications are highly important. Besides, the stimulus organism's response (SOR) model as Kamboj, Yadav & Rahman, (2018) noted the psychology of the environment proposes the different features of the environment like physical & nonphysical basics of a store can affect people's internal conditions & organism practices. Perceptual, psychological, feeling, & thinking actions initiate behavioral responses. pleasure, support, initiation, number of kinds of articles purchased & repurchase & the cost price paid are the outcomes of perceptual, psychological, feeling, & thinking action initiatives. Thus, behavioral responses, the number of items' purchase and repurchase & the amount of money spent in the store can be cultivated by virtual consumers' marketing communications (VCMC). Moreover, the data analysis result subject to virtual consumers' marketing communications to loyalty also proved a positive relationship. Therefore, virtual consumers' marketing communications' exert a positive effect on consumers' loyalty.

The moderating effect of cross-national culture incongruent language use specifically language difference on the relationship between virtual consumers' marketing communications, consumers' loyalty has prior literature proves. Hofstede's cultural dimension theory verified that differences of cultural components are the main causes for the variation of consumers' behavior to trust, satisfaction & loyalty. Gaps of understanding can create suspicion feelings when feeling uncertainty trust, satisfaction and loyalty cannot be realized. So, when one removes the degree of uncertainty, he /she become highly convinced of the matter.

5. Conclusion

This study investigated (a) the effects of virtual consumers' marketing communications on consumer loyalty; (b) how does language difference moderates the link within VCMC and consumer's loyalty? The above-mentioned investigations and relationships were proved by survey data gathered mainly from international consumers those who have cross-national culture and mobile commerce experiences in China. So far, this is my first attempt to aware and improves the links of international virtual consumers who have a cross-national culture to mobile commerce websites retails. The study has forwarded its investigations outputs that help to determine the main elements of virtual communications that have visible effects on virtual consumers' communications' effectiveness on mobile commerce websites retails. Specifically, this study demonstrated that how cross-national culture incongruent language use or language difference affects the communication effectiveness of virtual consumer's to the states of satisfaction & loyalty in China. Furthermore, the moderating role of cross-national culture incongruent language use or language difference that would influence communications effectiveness to loyalty has been forwarded.

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